

ABSTRACT

This study determined the students' learning in food and beverage services subjects using the three identified innovative teaching modalities, namely: modular approach, demo-video learning approach, and traditional lecture method, and its relationship to their preferred strategy in the selected schools in Surigao del Sur Division which offers Food and Beverage Services qualification during the Academic Year 2022-2023. This study used both the descriptive and quasi-experimental design of research. This study used both the descriptive and quasi-experimental methods of analysis. The study adopted a Learning Activity Sheet from DepEd Surigao del Sur for a modular approach. Also, an adopted video lesson was utilized by the researcher. In addition, the researcher uses a lesson plan for the classroom discussion. The results showed a significant difference in post-test mean scores between the three strategies, with Demo Video LA being the most effective. The findings suggest that educators should consider using various teaching strategies to meet the diverse needs of their students. The significant relationship between the preferred teaching strategy and the learning score highlights the importance of considering students' preferences when selecting teaching methods. Overall, the study adds to the growing body of literature on the positive impact of technology-based teaching strategies on student learning outcomes and underscores the need for educators to adopt innovative instructional practices that foster a positive learning environment and promote student engagement.

Keywords: *Preferred modality, video lesson, modular approach, traditional approach*

INTRODUCTION

The food and beverage service is a process of preparing, presenting, and serving food and beverages to customers. Food can include a wide range of styles and cuisine types. These can be classified by country. Beverages include all alcoholic and non-alcoholic drinks. Alcoholic beverages include wines and all other types of alcoholic drinks such as Cocktails, Beer, Ciders, Spirits, and Liqueurs. In the food service industry, there are a number of different industrial sectors and these are categorized according to the type of customer demand being met. This identification of sectors also provides a framework for those studying the food and beverage service industry to which further studies and experience may be related (Mondal, 2022).

In the context of service quality, it has long been a topic of interest to academics and researchers because customer satisfaction is directly related to service quality. According to research, a high degree of customer satisfaction leads to an increase in revenue. (Kumar et al., 2009). In order to have this quality of service, quality training and proper education and experience are required. Thus, educational institutions are spending billions to improve the quality of education (Barret et al., 2006). In addition, UNESCO (2012) fosters improved access, delivery, standards, innovations, and quality assurance at all levels from basic literacy to higher and continuing education.

Over the past few decades, the country has made great strides to improve access to education, particularly at the secondary level but still facing the problem of quality of education due to incompatibility between working conditions, teaching modality or strategies, and instructional materials (Ashraf, 2019). It is difficult for teachers to manage such courses, especially when they are tested by a diverse student body. They frequently have to give in and meet the demands of the students in order to protect the learning process (Farihah et al., 2019).

Carrascal National High School offers Food and Beverage Services as a specialization in the Technical Vocational and Livelihood Track. However, many students face significant challenges in mastering their skills, particularly in household services, which has resulted in consistently low performance. To address these difficulties, researchers have proposed various learning modalities as potential solutions. Grustan (2021) advocates strongly for the use of demo-videos as supplementary materials to enhance student performance. These instructional videos enable students to have control over their learning experience by allowing them to play and pause the content at their own pace. This increased autonomy and flexibility are likely to boost student motivation, thus improving their overall performance in the subject.

In addition, Buniel and Calipayan (2020) conducted a study that demonstrated effectiveness of contextualized modules in meeting students' needs, even in the absence of classroom teachers. These modules, utilized in distance learning approaches, have proven to be beneficial in enhancing students' academic performance. By enabling students to learn at their own pace and

providing them with tailored content, contextualized modules foster a more personalized learning experience.

Given the struggles faced by students in mastering the skills required for Food and Beverage Services, it becomes crucial to identify their preferences when it comes to teaching modalities. Such a study would allow educators to design instructional strategies that align with students' individual learning styles. By catering to these preferences, educators can create a more inclusive and student-centered learning environment, leading to increased engagement, motivation, and ultimately, improved academic outcomes.

With this, the researcher carried out a study that enabled us to ascertain from the perspective of the student which learning modalities they favor. Higher learning outcomes resulted from the use of supplemental instructional materials like modules and demo videos. The students' understanding and ability to reflect on the pertinent topics improved with the use of these instructional materials. It enhances students' academic performance, encourages learning, and makes them more independent in the learning process. Additionally, the focus of this research was on achieving and upholding excellence standards in engaging and enjoyable teaching and learning methods.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design. This study used both the descriptive and quasi-experimental design of research. The data collected in determining the students' preference in teaching modalities was described accordingly. In addition, quantifying the mean scores in pre-test and post-test of the students using the three identified innovative teaching strategies in teaching food and beverage services subject namely: modular approach, demo-video learning approach, and traditional learning approach, helped us determine the relationship of their preference to their academic achievement. Moreover, quantifying the preference of the students on their preferred teaching modalities will help us determine which among the three teaching strategies they preferred most.

Respondents. The respondents of the study were the Grade 12 students of Cantilan National High School, Carrascal National High School and Madrid National High School. Every school had only one section, therefore they were selected purposively. They were under heterogeneous group of students to ensure objective results of the study. In addition, 5 panel of evaluators were selected to evaluate and validate the supplementary instructional materials that will be used in this study. They were identified as master teachers and/or teacher experts in the field of food and beverage services qualification. Table below shows how the respondents are distributed.

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents

Respondents	No. of Respondents
Cantilan National High School	35
Carrascal National High School	30
Madrid National High School	30
Teacher-Experts	5
TOTAL	100

Data Collection Procedure. Firstly, the researcher obtained approval for the conduct of this study from the Schools Division Superintendent and principals of the selected schools offering Food and Beverage Services qualification. The application of the three innovative teaching methods was personally administered by the researcher to the participants. It was conducted to the three (3) identified schools namely Carrascal NHS, Cantilan NHS, and Madrid NHS.

Teaching using a modular learning approach was first conducted. The pre-test was facilitated before the presentation and post-test followed afterwards. The researcher gave the module to the students on the first topic which was the table skirting. The students read carefully all the contents and instructions in the module, and answered the necessary activities. The allotted time for the first topic was 1 hour.

Using the same group of students, the third topic was presented which was the napkin folding. The teacher now discussed or lectured the topic. Students interacted or asked questions to the teacher. The students performed on whatever the teacher ask them to do and listen to the discussion. The class had a duration of 1 hour only.

Then, using the same group of students, another topic was presented. The utilization of the demo-video was done in this learning approach. The teacher gave the demo-video to the students with

the topic table set-up, and the students followed all the instructions therein. Students were allowed to pause and play the video until they can accordingly. The students were given an hour to finish their independent learning. Afterwards, a post-test was given to them since the pre-test was already administered before the activity started.

After all the teaching modality was experienced by the students, the researcher then individually asked the students on which teaching modality they preferred most. Then, the researcher checked, recorded, tabulated, and analyzed all the data gathered with the help of the statistician for implications.

Data Analysis Procedure. This study utilized weighted mean to determine the scores (pre-tests and post-tests) of the respondents. Furthermore, this study utilized Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) to determine the effect of the treatment. The pre-test was used as covariate while the post-test was used as criterion measure. The ANCOVA was used because the respondents are not randomly chosen but they are intact sections. Lastly, t-test was used to examine whether or not the difference between two groups averages most likely reflects a real difference in the population from which the groups are sampled.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The findings presented in Table 2 demonstrate a positive trend in the mean scores of students across three different teaching strategies: Demo Video LA, Modular, and Lecture. A positive trend implies that the average scores of students increased over time.

Looking at the table, we can see that the pretest scores for Demo Video LA, Modular, and Lecture were 10.5593, 10.5652, and 10.6923 respectively. These scores indicate that all students had some level of prior learning or knowledge related to the topics covered in the study. The similarity in the pretest scores across the teaching strategies suggests that the students had a comparable baseline level of understanding before the intervention.

Examining the post-test scores in the table, we observe a range from 15.6923 to 18.2034. The Lecture method yielded the lowest post-test score, while the Demo Video LA method resulted in the highest score. This implies that students performed well when the Demo Video LA teaching strategy was utilized. The wider range of scores in the post-test indicates variations in the performance of students across the different teaching strategies. Overall, the findings suggest that all three teaching strategies were effective in improving students' scores. However, the Demo Video LA strategy stood out as particularly successful, as it resulted in the highest post-test scores. These results indicate the potential benefits of utilizing multimedia resources, such as demo videos, in the teaching process.

For the pre-test scores, the standard deviation ranges from 2.09701 to 2.45842. This means that the majority of the pre-test scores fall within this range, indicating a relatively narrow spread of scores. A smaller standard deviation suggests that the scores are clustered closely around the mean, indicating less variability among the pre-test scores. On the other hand, the post-test scores have a standard deviation ranging from 1.34907 to 2.28709. This range suggests that the post-test scores have a slightly wider spread compared to the pre-test scores. The larger standard deviation implies that the post-test scores exhibit more variability or dispersion, with some scores deviating further from the mean. Overall, comparing the ranges of standard deviations indicates that the post-test scores have a slightly greater spread or variability compared to the pre-test scores.

The results of this study are consistent with prior research conducted by Lani (2014), Ozaslan and Maden (2013), and Stepp-Greany (2002) which demonstrated the positive impact of technology-based teaching methods on student learning outcomes. The use of visual aids such as video lessons or modules has been shown to improve students' retention of course material, which is reflected in their improved test scores.

Moreover, the benefits of technology integration in the classroom extend beyond academic achievement. Stepp-Greany (2002) highlights several advantages, such as increased motivation, enhanced self-concept and mastery of basic skills, more student-centered learning, and greater engagement in the learning process. These outcomes are critical for fostering a positive learning environment and ensuring that students are actively involved in their own education. Overall, the findings of this study add to the growing body of literature supporting the use of technology-based teaching strategies in the classroom. Teachers can incorporate a variety of visual aids and multimedia resources to enhance their instructional practices and promote student learning.

Table 2. Pretest and Posttest Mean Score of the Three Groups

Teaching Strategy	Mean		SD	
	Pre-Test	Post-test	Pre-test	Post-test
Demo Video LA	10.5593	18.2034	2.45842	1.34907
Modular	10.5652	17.0000	2.27289	2.11058
Lecture	10.6923	15.6923	2.09701	2.28709

Table 3 displays various statistical measures related to the pre-test and post-test scores of three different teaching strategies: Demo Video LA, Modular, and Lecture. These measures include the mean scores, standard deviations, F-values, and p-values. Looking at the pre-test mean scores, we can observe that they were quite similar for all three teaching strategies, ranging from 10.5593 to 10.6923. This indicates that, on average, students in each group had comparable levels of knowledge or understanding before the intervention.

The standard deviations, ranging from 2.09701 to 2.45842, represent the degree of variability or spread of the pre-test scores within each group. To determine if there were any significant differences in the pre-test mean scores among the three teaching strategies, a one-way ANOVA test was conducted. The result of this test produced an F-value of 0.017 and a corresponding p-value of 0.983. In statistical analysis, the F-value is used to assess whether the means of different groups are significantly different. The p-value indicates the probability of obtaining these results by chance alone.

In this case, the F-value of 0.017 suggests a very small value, while the p-value of 0.983 indicates a high probability. Therefore, there is no significant difference observed among the pre-test mean scores of the three teaching strategies. This suggests that, before the intervention, the groups were comparable in terms of their knowledge levels. In conclusion, the findings from the statistical analysis of the pre-test scores indicate that there were no significant differences among the mean scores of the three teaching strategies. This implies that the groups were fairly equivalent at the beginning of the study, providing a solid foundation for comparison and evaluation of the teaching interventions (Ozaslan & Maden, 2013).

After the implementation of the teaching strategies, the post-test mean scores showed a significant difference between the groups. The Demo Video LA group had the highest mean score of 18.2034, with a standard deviation of 1.34907. The Modular group had an average mean score of 17.0000 with a standard deviation of 2.11058, while the Lecture group had an average mean score of 15.6923 with a standard deviation of 2.28709.

A statistical test was conducted on the post-test scores, resulting in an F-value of 13.295 and a p-value of 0.000. This indicates that there is a significant difference between the post-test mean scores of the three teaching strategies. The F-value measures the extent of variation among the groups, and a larger F-value suggests a greater difference. The p-value indicates the probability of obtaining these results by chance alone, and a small p-value suggests that the observed differences are not due to random chance. Therefore, based on the statistical analysis, it can be concluded that the teaching strategies used had a significant impact on student learning outcomes. The Demo Video LA group, in particular, achieved the highest mean score, indicating the effectiveness of this teaching strategy in enhancing student performance (Lani, 2014).

Hence, the study found that Demo Video LA was the preferred teaching strategy in terms of improving student learning outcomes, as reflected in the significant increase in post-test mean scores. This result is supported by the student's responses during the interview, "*I really like the Demo Video LA since I can pose it and replay it whenever I wanted to master the topic*", "*Demo Video LA provides an engaging learning experience beyond lectures, making it enjoyable and memorable.*", "*Demo Video LA accommodates different learning styles, enhancing understanding and boosting comprehension.*", "*Demo Video LA revolutionizes learning by promoting critical thinking and problem-solving skills through interactive videos.*", and "*Demo Video LA makes subjects exciting and engaging, encouraging us to explore and think creatively.*". The Modular and Lecture strategies also led to improved mean scores, although to a lesser extent. These findings provide valuable insights for educators looking to enhance their instructional practices and improve student learning outcomes (Stepp-Greany, 2002).

Table 3. Significant Values on the Difference Between the Mean Scores of the Three Groups

Pretest	Mean	SD	F-value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Demo Video LA	10.5593	2.45842	.017	.983	Failed to reject H ₀	There is no significant difference
Modular	10.5652	2.27289				
Lecture	10.6923	2.09701				
Posttest	Mean	SD	F-value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Demo Video LA	18.2034	1.34907	13.295	0.000	Reject H ₀	There is significant difference
Modular	17.0000	2.11058				
Lecture	15.6923	2.28709				

The significant value of 0.000 and the rejection of the null hypothesis indicate that there is a significant relationship between the preferred teaching strategy and the learning score. The correlation coefficient of 0.474 indicates a moderate positive relationship between the two variables. This finding suggests that the teaching strategy used by the instructor has an impact on the learning outcomes of the students. It also implies that students may have a preferred learning style or teaching method that is more effective for them. Therefore, educators should consider the preferences of their students when selecting a teaching strategy or method to use in their classrooms.

The results of this study are consistent with previous research that has found a relationship between teaching strategies and learning outcomes. For example, a study by Lai and Kritsonis (2006) found that students who were taught using a variety of teaching strategies had higher levels of academic achievement than those who were taught using a single method. The significant relationship found between the preferred teaching strategy and the learning score suggests that educators should consider using a variety of teaching strategies to meet the diverse needs of their students. By doing so, they may be able to improve the learning outcomes of their students and help them achieve academic success.

Table 4. Significant Values on the Relationship Between the Preferred Teaching Strategy and the Learning Score

	Rho	p-value	n	Decision	Interpretation
Teaching Strategy and Score	0.474	0.000	95	Reject H ₀	There is significant relationship

CONCLUSION

The study provides evidence supporting the use of technology-based teaching strategies, such as Demo Video LA, Modular, and Lecture, in enhancing student learning outcomes. The results showed a significant difference in post-test mean scores between the three strategies, with Demo Video LA being the most effective. The findings also suggest that educators should consider using a variety of teaching strategies to meet the diverse needs of their students. The significant relationship found between the preferred teaching strategy and the learning score highlights the importance of considering students' preferences when selecting teaching methods. Overall, the study adds to the growing body of literature on the positive impact of technology-based teaching strategies on student learning outcomes and underscores the need for educators to adopt innovative instructional practices that foster a positive learning environment and promote student engagement.

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